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INSON HUQUQLARINI O`RNI VA AHAMIYATI.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada inson huquqlarini himoya qilish mexanizmi, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasida inson huquqlarini himoya qilish shart sharoitlari haqida tushuncha beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: huquq, burch, konstitutsiya, qonun, erkinlik

Inson jamiyat va davlat hayotining barcha sohalarida davlat qonunlarida mustahkamlangan o'z huquqi, erkinligi va burchlarini amalga oshirishi bilan qatnashadi. Jamiyat va davlat insonning huquqi va erkinligi, uning shani va qadr qimmatini oliy qadriyat sifatida e'tirof etadi. Bu bosh qomusimizning 13-moddasida o'z aksini topgan. Unga ko'ra: "O'zbekiston Respublikasida demokratiya umuminsoniy prinsiplarga asoslanadi, unga ko'ra inson, uning hayoti, erkinligi, sha'ni, qadr-qimmati va boshqa daxlsiz huquqlari oliy qadriyat hisoblanadi". Konstitutsiya inson huquqlari va erkinliklarini ta'minlanishini birinchi o'ringa qo'yadi, shaxsning ma'muriybuyruqbozlik tizimining bir muruvvati, belgilangan maqsadga erishishning oddiygina bir vositasi deb hisoblamaydi. "Konstitutsiyaviy huquq va erkinliklar har bir shaxs va o'zbekistonning har bir fuqarosi uchun taalluqlidir. Asosiy huquq, erkinlik va burchlarning o'ziga xos xususiyati shundaki, ular hech bir istisnosiz har bir kishi yoki har bir fuqaro uchun teng va birdir. Davlat u yoki bu asosiy huquqni tan olishida ularni hamma tomonidan amalga oshirish imkoniyatining huquqiy zaminini yaratadi." Konstitutsiyamizning shaxs yoki fuqaroning huquq va erkinliklari haqidagi bobi aniq huquq va erkinliklarga bag'ishlangan bo'lib, undagi moddalar mantiqiy tizimni tashkil etadi. Bular huquq va erkinliklarning, shaxs va fuqarolar turmush darajalarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini ifoda etadi. Mana shu belgilarga asoslanib konstitutsiyaviy huquq va erkinliklarni uch guruhga: a)shaxsiy; b) siyosiy; d) ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy huquqlarga bo'lish mumkin. Shaxsiy huquq va erkinliklar inson erkinligining asosiy jabhalarini qamrab oladi, kishining jamiyatdagi turmushi, yashash va faoliyat ko'rsatish asoslarini ifodalaydi, uning shaxsiy hayotini, xususiy erkinliklarini turli xildagi aralshuvlardan himoya qiladi. Inson hayoti-qonun tomonidan qo'riqlanadigan oliy ijtimoiy ahamiyatga molik qadriyatdir. Harbir shaxs yashash huquqiga ega bo'lib, hech kim uni o'zboshimchalik bilan mahrum etish mumkin emas. Bosh qomusimizning 24-moddasida ham bu o'z qonunini tasdig'ini topgan."Yashash

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huquqi hr bir insonng uzviy huquqidir. Inson hayotiga suiqasd qilish eng og'ir jinoyatdir" . Mamlakatimizda 2008-yil 1-yanvardan buyon o'lim jazosining bekor qilinganligi ham inson hayoi, uning qadr qimmati har narsadan ustun ekanligini amalda yana bir bor tasdiqladi. Insonning jamiyatda tutgan o'rni uning shaxsiy huquq va erkinlilar bilan birga, uning siyosiy huquqlaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlari bilan ham belgilanadi. Siyosiy huquqlar har bir shaxsning jamiyatning siyosiy hayoti va munosabatlarida qanday ishtirok qilishini belgilab beradi. Har bir voyaga yetganm to'liq muomala layoqatiga ega bo'lgan "O'zbekiston Respublikasi fuqarolari kasaba uyushmalariga, siyosiy partiyalarga va boshqa jamoat birlashmalariga uyushish, ommaviy harakatlarda ishtirok etish huquqiga ega" - deya bosh qomusimizda ta'kidlab o'tilgan. Har bir shaxs o'zining siyosiy tashkilotlar yoki jamoat birlashmalariga a'zo bo'lish huquqidan qanchalik samarali foydalansa, bu uning siyosiy jihatdan yetuk bo'lishida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Insonning siyosiy tashkilotlar va jamoat birlashmalaridagi faol ishtiroki uning o'zligini anglash va himoya qilish imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi. Siyosiy huqularda insonning ijtimoiy tengligi o'z aksini topadi. Barcha fuqarolarning siyosiy huquqlardan samarali foydalanish imkoniyatlari bunday tenglikning amaliy ifodasidir. Iqtisodiy huquq o'z mohiyatiga ko'ra muayyan ijtimoiy boylikka nisbatan huquqqa ega bo'lishdir. Bunday ijtimoiy boyliklar turli xilda bo'lib, ular fuqarolarning siyosiy, moddiy va ma'naviy ehtiyojlarining qondirilishini ko'zda tutadi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasining 41-moddasiga muvofiq," har kim bilim olish huquqiga ega. Davlat bepul umumiy ta'lim olishni kafolatlaydi. Maktab ishlari davlat nazoratida". Ta'lim inson shaxsining to'la rivojlanishiga va uning hurmatini joyiga qo'yishga qaratilishi, har kim jamiyatning foyda keltiruvchi erkin ishtirokchisi bo'lishiga imkon yaratib berishi, barcha xalqlar, irq, etnik va diniy guruhlar o'rtasida do'stlik va hurmatini qaror toptirishga ko'maklashishi zarur. Ta'lim to'g'risidagi qonunning 4-moddasiga muvofiq har kimning kelib chiqishi, jinsi, jinsi, tili, Yoshi, irqi, milliy mansubligidan, e'tiqodi, dinga munosabati, ijtimoiy ahvoli, mashg'ulotlat turi, respublika hududida qancha vaqt yashayotganidan qat'iy nazar, har kimga bilim olishda teng huquqlar kafolatlanadi". Har bir fuqaro huquq va erkinliklardan unumli foydalanib, o'z vaqtida konstitutsiyada belgilab qo'yilgan burchlarini vijdonan bajarsa davlat, jamiyat, xalq manfaatlariga putur yetmaydi. Biz ko'zlagan" Ozod va obod vatan, erkin va farovon hayotni barpo etish" g'oyasini to'la ravishga jamiyat hayotiga tatbiq etamiz.

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